

EXPERIMENTAL AND ANALYTICAL STUDY OF COMPOSITE LATTICE STRUCTURE FOR FUTURE JAPANESE LAUNCHERS

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1 Introduction

Weight reduction and cost reduction are the main issues to be improved for all the launcher structures. JAXA is now studying the system concept for the next flagship launcher [1] which will be alternative to the existing H-IIA and H-IIB, in which it is necessary to get international competitiveness of launch capability and cost. In structural technical field, increasing application of composite structures is considered to be the most promising approach to reduce the structural weight and cost.

Composite lattice structure is the structural concept which consists of helical and hoop ribs intersecting each other in a regular pattern. Under compressive and bending load, helical ribs are the main load carrying path using their unidirectional properties, and out-of-plane deformation of helical ribs are supported by hoop ribs by their unidirectional tensile properties, so it is very efficient structural concept for composite structure using under such loading conditions.

The purpose of this study is to develop a low-cost manufacturing process of composite lattice structure, and to investigate the mechanical properties and buckling properties using the large-size manufacturing demonstrator. With experimental and analytical approach, to establish the design and manufacturing guideline is also the future goal of this study.

Usually, the building block approach is adopted for such activities, especially in the field of aerospace applications. But we think it more efficient and reasonable for us to manufacture a full scale demonstrator to evaluate the design and analysis, properties of the material, and manufacturing method. From this point of view, we choose this approach in this study.

2 Experiment

2.1 Design

The design load was set at 1500 kN compression which was typical for upper stage structure of large launchers. We chose simple cylindrical shape for the demonstrator with diameter of 2.5 m and length of 2.0 m as shown in Fig. 1. For this design situation, we applied the numerical design procedure to decide the number of helical and hoop ribs, and the thickness and the width of the ribs to minimize the mass of cylindrical lattice shell, which was described in other studies [2].

For the preliminary design, three constraint equations were to be considered which described the critical global buckling force of the shell, P_c , the critical local buckling force of helical ribs, P_l , and the critical force due to the compressive strength of helical ribs, P_s :

$$P_c = 2\pi H^2 \cos^2 \varphi \sqrt{E^2 \frac{2b_h b_c}{3a_h a_c}} \quad (1)$$

$$P_l = \frac{1}{3} k \pi^3 ERH \left(\frac{b_h}{a_h} \right)^3 \sin^2(2\varphi) \cos^2 \varphi \quad (2)$$

$$P_s = 4\pi \bar{\sigma} RH \frac{b_h}{a_h} \cos^2 \varphi \quad (3)$$

The considered objective function was the mass of the shell M that could be expressed as:

$$M = 2\pi RLH \left(2\rho_h \frac{b_h}{a_h} + \rho_c \frac{b_c}{a_c} \right) \quad (4)$$

where, H is the rib thickness, φ is the helical angle to the shell axis, E is the modulus of elasticity of ribs, a_h and a_c are the distance of helical and hoop ribs, b_h and b_c are the width of helical and hoop ribs, R and L are the shell radius and height, k is a buckling coefficient, $\bar{\sigma}$ is the compressive strength of helical ribs, ρ_h and ρ_c are the mass densities of helical and hoop ribs, respectively.

Fig. 2 shows the design parameters of the lattice ribs. We decided the design variables to minimize M in the range where P_c , P_l and P_s were larger than the design compressive axial load, P .

Finally, the values represented in Fig. 3 were set for the demonstrator. In this design, the weight of this structure was predicted about 32 kg.

Fig. 1. The dimension of demonstrator.

Fig. 2. Design variables of the ribs.

Radius	R	1250mm
Hight	L	2000mm
Number of hoop ribs	N_c	15
Number of helical ribs	N_h	71
Helical rib angle	φ	21.4deg
Distance of hoop ribs	a_c	142.9mm
Distance of helical ribs	a_h	104.4mm
Width of hoop ribs	b_c	5.7mm
Width of helical ribs	b_h	4.7mm
Rib thickness	H	10mm

Fig. 3. Design variables set for the demonstrator.

2.2 Manufacturing

In order to decide the manufacturing process for full scale demonstrator, it was essential to understand the impact of the process on its strength and stiffness, especially of the intersecting point of the helical and the hoop ribs. So in the first step, we conducted some trial fabrication for smallest repetitive unit of lattice shell. Basically, we tried some prepreg-based processes and wet winding processes, and compared them by compressive tests and CT inspections. As a result, we chose the wet winding process for the full scale demonstrator, which was considered to be the most well-balanced in the quality and manufacturing cost. The test piece fabricated by the wet winding process trial is shown in Fig. 4. There was almost no void formation observed in the result of CT inspection for the intersecting point of the ribs in this test piece, which is shown in Fig. 5.

The most important issue for manufacturing this structure is how to make a flat surface at the rib intersecting point without misalignment of the fibers. Fiber misalignment or buildup around the rib intersecting point is undesirable for the structure, because such phenomenon leads to significant loss of strength and stiffness. From this point of view, we used silicon rubber blocks as the expansion tooling, which provide lateral compaction of the ribs during cure. The image of the expansion tooling is shown in Fig. 6. As a result, we could prevent a buildup at the intersecting points as shown in Fig. 4.

The low-cost aspects of the manufacturing process developed in this study are shown below:

Fig. 8. The winding process.

Fig. 9. The full-scale demonstrator.

2.3 Unit tests

In combination with the full scale demonstrator, we also manufactured the partial cylindrical piece which is about one-sixth of a cylinder as shown in Fig. 10. Using this part, we conducted some compressive tests and 4 point bending tests for helical ribs. The compressive test specimens included two types which were with and without rib intersecting point (knot) as shown in Fig. 11. Each test specimen was

20 mm for gage length, and stainless tabs of 50 mm length were fixed by adhesive and fasteners on both ends. The result of the tests for ribs without knot is shown in Fig. 12, and for ribs with knot is shown in Fig. 13. These results show that compressive strength and stiffness of ribs are higher than the values used in the preliminary design (Axial stiffness is 80 GPa and compressive strength is 450 MPa), but the compressive strength of ribs with knot show significant decrease. So we evaluated the fiber volume fraction of the ribs by microscopic observation. The results of V_f were about 30% for ribs, and about 60% for intersecting point as shown in Fig. 14. This value was reasonable compared with other studies, but there were some voids in the intersecting point. So this may cause the decrease of compressive strength.

The 4 point bending test specimens were cut out from helical ribs without knot, which dimension is shown in Fig. 15. Test results for flexural stiffness is shown in Fig. 16 and for flexural strength is shown in Fig. 17. These results shows that flexural stiffness is lower than compressive stiffness, on the other hand flexural strength is higher than compressive strength.

We also conducted the compressive tests for the smallest repetitive unit shown in Fig. 18. It shows the in-plane buckling is the critical mode, so the rib width and axial stiffness are the critical parameters.

Fig. 10. Partial cylindrical piece.

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Fig. 11. The compressive test specimens.

Fig. 14. The fiber volumetric fraction.

	Mean	Standard deviation
Axial stiffness	84.7 GPa	2.9 GPa
Compressive strength	529.2 MPa	42.0 MPa

Fig. 12. Test results for ribs without knot.

Fig. 15. The 4 point bending test specimen.

	Mean	Standard deviation
Compressive strength	293.2 MPa	55.5 MPa

Fig. 13. Test results for ribs with knot.

Fig. 16. Flexural stiffness of the ribs.

Fig. 17. Flexural strength of the ribs.

Fig. 18. Repetitive unit test and buckling mode.

Fig. 19. First mode of the test.

Fig. 20. Second mode of the test.

2.4 Modal testing and analysis

Before the full-scale compressive test, we conducted the modal test and analysis to confirm the dynamic characteristics of the lattice structure. Test method was the impact hammer test to evaluate the vibration property and stiffness of the lattice structure.

The first and second vibration mode of the test is shown in Fig. 19 and Fig. 20, respectively. These low-frequency modal shapes were the circumferential mode.

In the analysis, the first and second vibration mode were the same as the test result, but the natural frequencies were slightly lower than that, as shown in Fig. 21 and Fig. 22. This result means that the structural stiffness of the demonstrator is higher than that of analytical model.

Fig. 21. First mode of the analysis.

Fig. 22. Second mode of the analysis.

demonstrator which type of buckling pattern would occur.

Fig. 23. Full view of the analysis model.

2.5 Full scale test

2.5.1 FEM analysis for the test

FEM analysis was conducted for the full-scale test configuration of the demonstrator in the purpose of predicting the buckling load and buckling shape in the test. The analysis tool we used was ANSYS14.0, modeled by SOLID185 elements. Full view of the analysis model is shown in Fig. 23. Each layer of the rib was modeled as shown in Fig. 24.

The first buckling mode of the analysis result is shown in Fig. 25 in which the buckling load is 427 kN. The buckling load of this mode was significantly lower than that of preliminary design formulation represented as (1), because it showed the non-axisymmetric shape.

On the other hand, first axisymmetric mode which is shown in Fig. 26 is the 251st mode in which the buckling load is 1080 kN, that is near to the result of formulation (1).

From this analysis results, it was predicted that the global buckling of the test would occur at 427 kN compression in the non-axisymmetric mode, which shape was “spiral buckling” mode. This spiral buckling mode was different from typical non-axisymmetric mode of “double sine mode”.

Double sine mode is the typical non-axisymmetric mode, in case there is no imperfection or anisotropic characteristics, as shown in Fig. 27. It could depend on the manufacturing or loading imperfection of the

L : Longitudinal direction
 T : Transverse direction

Rib laminated constitution

- ① [■(ϕ) / □ / ■(ϕ) / □ / ... / ■(ϕ) / □]
- ② [■(- ϕ) / □ / ■(- ϕ) / □ / ... / ■(- ϕ) / □]
- ③ [□ / ■(T) / □ / ■(T) / ... / □ / ■(T)]

Rib intersection laminated constitution

- ④ [■(ϕ) / ■(T) / ■(ϕ) / ■(T) / ... / ■(ϕ) / ■(T)]
- ⑤ [■(- ϕ) / ■(T) / ■(- ϕ) / ■(T) / ... / ■(- ϕ) / ■(T)]
- ⑥ [■(ϕ) / ■(- ϕ) / ■(ϕ) / ■(- ϕ) / ... / ■(ϕ) / ■(- ϕ)]

□ Resin layer, ■ Fiber with resin layer(ϕ , $-\phi$, T)
 • the thickness of each layer: 0.263mm
 • $\phi = 21.37^\circ$

Fig. 24. Modeling of ribs.

Fig. 25. First buckling mode (spiral shape).

Fig. 26. Axisymmetric buckling mode (251st).

Fig. 27. Typical buckling pattern of double sine.

2.4.2 Test result

Full-scale compressive test for this demonstrator was conducted to check the global stiffness and buckling load.

The test equipment is shown in Fig. 27. The upper bound of the demonstrator was fixed to the upper structure by bolted joints, and the lower bound of the

demonstrator was fixed to the loading structure. The loading structure was lifted up by the hydraulic jack which was set on the center of the axis. The upper structure was supported by 8 support posts which was fixed to the base structure, then compression was loaded to the demonstrator. Fig. 28 shows the full view of the test.

In this test, we measured 208 points of rib strains, 20 points of displacements, and compressive force of load cell.

The load-displacement curve measured in the test is shown in Fig. 29. The global stiffness of the test was 178 kN/mm, while FEM analysis result was 153 kN/mm. The global stiffness of the test was slightly greater than that of FEM analysis, so the manufacturing quality seemed fine in the global point of view, and the modeling of this lattice structure was verified.

In this test, global buckling was occurred at 420 kN of compressive load. The first buckling mode of FEM analysis was 427 kN, so they showed rather good agreement between the analysis and the test result.

The buckling was occurred at rather narrow region of the circumference of the shell, as shown in Fig. 30. This was probably in conjunction with normal manufacturing or loading imperfections.

After the global buckling occurred, the fracture in some ribs were immediately happened. The rib fracture distribution is shown with red marker in Fig. 31. This fracture in the ribs were thought to be an immediate effect of this buckling failure and the consequent loading redistribution. The important point was that the fractured helical ribs were distributed inclined along the cylinder, which seemed to show good agreement with the buckling mode shape of the spiral buckling pattern in the FEM analysis, rather than double sine pattern. So in this demonstrator, the spiral buckling mode was the critical mode for compressive loading.

The typical strain data is shown in Fig. 32 for helical ribs and Fig. 33 for hoop ribs. For helical ribs, average strain (axial compressive strain) was smaller than the analysis result, and bending strain was much larger than the analysis result. For hoop ribs, average strain (axial tensile strain) showed good agreement with the analysis, but bending strain was also much larger than the analysis result. The hoop ribs seemed to be effective because they showed the strain level as predicted.

This data also shows that the local buckling of helical ribs and hoop ribs occurred ahead of the global buckling. This local buckling mode seemed to be the rotational mode around the rib intersecting point. So this local buckling mode and the larger bending stress of the ribs were considered to be the result of insufficient stiffness of rib intersecting point (rotating stiffness).

Fig. 27. The test equipment.

Fig. 29. The load-displacement curve of the test.

Fig. 28. The full view of the test.

Fig. 30. The global buckling of the shell.

Fig. 31. The distribution of fractured ribs.

Fig. 32. Typical strain data of helical ribs.

Fig. 33. Typical strain data of hoop ribs.

References

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3 Conclusion

The possibility of applying low-cost composite lattice structures for launcher structure is shown in this study by manufacturing the large scale demonstrator and conducting some element tests and full-scale tests with analytical approach.

The low-cost manufacturing process based on the wet winding method was developed, and it was proven that the process we set were suitable for this structure, and the mechanical properties were successfully evaluated.

Then the vibration properties and buckling properties were tested by full-scale demonstrator, and analytical approach by FEM is verified.